

NAVIGATING ACADEMIC SUCCESS: INSIGHTS FROM ADVISORS ON THE
RETENTION OF FIRST-GENERATION COLLEGE STUDENTS

by

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December 2024

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ABSTRACT

First-generation college students often face unique challenges that can hinder their academic success. A qualitative study was conducted to explore the relationship between academic advisors and the retention of first-generation college students. Through in-depth interviews, this study aimed to uncover the challenges faced by first-generation college students and the strategies academic advisors employ to support them. The analysis was framed through Rendon's Validation Theory, emphasizing the importance of validation in fostering student success. Findings revealed that first-generation college students require some level of social, psychological, and academic support to be successful. Advisors expressed that while student groups can be beneficial to aid in community and a sense of belonging, they are not always a necessity for every first-generation student.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

I would like to express my heartfelt gratitude to the faculty at USM, whose guidance and support were invaluable throughout this capstone project. I am also thankful to Abilene Christian University for allowing me the opportunity to conduct this study at their institution.

A special thanks go to my classmates and peers who provided a collaborative environment and shared their knowledge during our informal discussions. I appreciate my former professors and colleagues from other universities for their insight and suggestions during my research.

DEDICATION

I dedicate this capstone to my family, whose unwavering support and encouragement have been the foundation of my academic journey. To my village, who instilled in me the value of education and perseverance, I am forever grateful. I also dedicate this work to my friends and mentors, who have inspired me with their wisdom and guidance throughout this process. Your belief in my abilities has motivated me to strive for excellence and to continue reaching for my dreams. As a first-generation college student, I dedicate this to all of you who have bravely embarked on your collegiate journey, breaking barriers, and redefining what is possible. May your determination and resilience continue to be an inspiration to the future generations. This research shall serve as a celebration of your accomplishments and a reminder that you are not alone.

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CHAPTER I — INTRODUCTION

Student advising is a crucial component of a college education, particularly for first-generation college students (Neuhauser & Weber, 2011). These students are often the first in their families to attend college and may lack the guidance and support that comes with having family members who have gone through the process before. First-generation college students may face several challenges that can impact their academic performance. These can include financial difficulties, cultural differences, and a lack of familiarity with the academic system and college culture (Arch & Gilman, 2019). Advisors can play an important role in helping these students navigate the challenges of college, achieve academic success, and improve retention rates (Alzen et al., 2021).

One important role of advisors is to help students choose the correct courses and majors. Many first-generation college students may not be familiar with the different options available to them or may not have a clear idea of what they want to study. Advisors can help students explore their interests and abilities and guide them toward majors and courses that align with their goals. Advisors can also help students navigate the academic system and understand the requirements for graduation. This can include helping students understand the different types of course offerings and credits, explaining the grading system, and aiding them in the development of their schedule to ensure they are on track to graduate on time. In their practice, advisors provide guidance on a range of other issues that can impact students' success. For example, they can assist in locating financial aid and scholarships that are accessible to the student, connect them with tutoring and practical support services, guide career planning and job search strategies, and navigate the stressors of everyday life.

Background

First-generation college student retention strategies have been a topic of concern in higher education for many years. This population of students matriculates at much lower rates than continuing-generation students. First-generation students, on average, finish in roughly six years while continuing-generation students finish in four (Arch & Gilman, 2019). Students whose parents do not hold four-year degrees are defined as first-generation college students (Stephens et al., 2014). For purposes of this study, all other students will be referred to as continuing-generation students. While there is no one-size-fits-all solution to this issue, there are some current trends that can be identified. One trend is the increased focus on providing support services specifically designed for first-generation college students. These services can include academic and success advising, mentoring, tutoring, and financial aid counseling. By providing these services, colleges and universities are hoping to improve retention rates among first-generation students.

The use of technology as a support metric for this population is another aspect. For example, some institutions are using data analytics to identify students who may be at risk of dropping out and then targeting them with additional support services. Another example includes the use of technology in how the success advisor communicates with the student (Baird, 2020). There is a growing recognition of the importance of creating a sense of community among first-generation college students. Many institutions are implementing programs that bring first-generation students together, such as peer mentoring programs and first-generation student organizations. Finally, some institutions are experimenting with innovative approaches to improve first-generation college student retention rates. For example, some colleges and universities are implementing programs

that allow first-generation students to take a gap year before starting college, which can help them better prepare for the academic and social challenges of college life while maintaining communication with their advisors.

Both academic advisors and student success advisors work with students to help them thrive in the collegiate environment, but there are some differences between the two roles. Academic advisors typically focus on helping students navigate the academic requirements of their degree programs (Neuhauser & Weber, 2011). They may help students plan their schedules, choose, and register for courses, and ensure that they are meeting degree requirements. They may also provide information on academic policies and procedures, help students understand their academic standing, and refer students to campus resources as needed. Student success advisors, on the other hand, tend to take a more holistic approach to student success (Neuhauser & Weber, 2011). They may work with students on a variety of issues that can impact their academic performance, such as time management, study skills, stress management, and goal setting. They may also help students connect with resources on campus that can support their success, such as tutoring services, counseling services, and career services. Academic advisors tend to focus more on academic planning and requirements, while Student success advisors focus more on helping students develop the skills and strategies they need to succeed academically and personally. For this study, the focus is on academic advisors.

Problem Statement

First-generation college students, or students whose parents did not obtain a four-year degree, may face several challenges that can make it more difficult for them to graduate. Because of this, the retention rate for first-generation students is relatively

lower than continuing continuing-generation students. These challenges, outlined below, are financial difficulties, lack of familiarity with college culture, balancing responsibilities, and lack of preparation (Arch & Gilman, 2019). First-generation college students may not have as much financial support from their families, making it harder for them to afford tuition, textbooks, and other expenses associated with college (Arch & Gilman, 2019). This can lead to stress and distractions that can affect their academic performance and progress. Their lack of familiarity with college culture and expectations as students whose parents have attended college makes it harder for them to navigate college life, including understanding academic requirements, seeking out resources, and knowing how to network with professors and peers. Additionally, first-generation college students may have family responsibilities, such as caring for younger siblings or working to support their families (Arch & Gilman, 2019). This can make it difficult for them to balance their academic responsibilities with their other obligations. Last, first-generation college students may not have had the same academic preparation as their peers who attended schools with more resources (Arch & Gilman, 2019). This can make it harder for them to keep up with coursework and succeed academically.

Purpose Statement

The purpose of this study is to better understand the challenges that first-generation college students face and what role academic advisors play in their retention. Specifically, the study will address how significant, if any, the relationship is between first-generation college students and academic advisors. The study also investigates the approaches taken by advisors to provide the necessary support to this population of students.

Research Questions

This research was guided by three research questions:

1. What challenges do first-generation college students face in their collegiate experience?
2. What is the relationship between retention and advising interventions for first-generation college student populations?
3. Are first-generation student groups effective in supporting students?

Definition of Terms

First-Generation College Students – commonly defined as those whose parents did not graduate with a bachelor’s degree (Arch & Gilman, 2019).

Continuing-Generation College Students – A student who has at least one parent with some post-secondary education experience (Redford & Mulvaney Hoyer, 2017).

IGEN - A first-generation college student success program that provides students with dedicated resources such as peer mentoring, special interest workshops, and phased programming for all four years of their undergraduate degree. The goal is to build a support system that enables students to rise above obstacles and achieve success (*First-Generation Student Success Program, 2023*).

Assumptions

For this study, it was assumed that all advisors would be honest and unbiased about their approaches to advising first-generation college students in their caseload. This qualitative study also functioned under the assumption that the interviews conducted would be sufficient to yield insight into the individual experiences of the advisors and their perspectives on the issues that impact the retention of first-generation college

students. Lastly, it was assumed that the advisors would articulate their thoughts in such a way that the researcher perceived the response as intended.

Limitations

Limitations that are outside of the scope of control of the researcher for this study include the sample size. Although it is a large institution there are only 13 undergraduate academic advisors, leaving only a small number of possible interviews. Of the 13 advisors, only 6 participated in the study. This limits the results from being generalized to all advisors with a first-generation college student population. Other limitations include the structure of the institution in which the study was conducted. It further limits the generalization of the results. Lastly, there was the temporal constraint of time and the idea that the retention rates of this population can or will change over time.

Delimitations

The scope of this study does not extend beyond a single institution, ACU. This should be noted as a delimitation to ensure contextual relevance when comparing results. The semi-structured interviews allowed for an extensive exploration of the advisors' perspectives while maintaining a comparable dataset for analysis.

Conclusion

Academic advising is important to the success of first-generation college students. By providing guidance and support in a range of areas, advisors can help these students overcome the challenges of college and achieve their academic and career goals. Higher education institutions are working to address these challenges and provide support for first-generation college students. This includes providing financial assistance, improving access to technology, and offering academic and emotional support services. This study

sought to understand the relationship, if any, and its significance between academic advising and the retention of first-generation college students.

CHAPTER II — LITERATURE REVIEW

This literature review explores the history of the study of first-generation (first-gen) students, the challenges they face, and the framework used in best practices to tailor advising approaches to each student to maximize success. First-generation students and their increased attrition can be a difficult hurdle to overcome in higher education (Kezar et al., 2022). Research shows that college enrollment and retention rates vary based on the level of education the student's parents have received (Peralta & Klonowski, 2017). In other words, students whose parents have little to no experience with higher education withdraw at much higher rates than continuing-generation students (McCulloh, 2022; Palbusa & Gauvain, 2017; Peralta & Klonowski, 2017; Ward et al., 2012).

The study of first-generation college students dates back to the late 2000s (Davis, 2010). Before then American colleges and universities failed to keep up with enrollment numbers relative to this population due to the lack of understanding that there was a critical need for attention to this population (Davis, 2010). In the early 2010s, there was an upward trend in access to higher education affording more first-generation students the opportunity to attend a four-year institution (Peralta & Klonowski, 2017). In 2010, 4.5 million students in higher education enrollment were identified as first-generation students (Schelbe et al., 2019). The high enrollment numbers and data collection began to shed light on the challenges faced in comparison to continuing generation students, as first-generation students are less likely to still be enrolled after four years and more likely to discontinue their studies after their first year causing retention rates to be significantly lower (Schelbe et al., 2019). As enrollment increases, higher education institutions are

seeking both standard and alternative approaches to academic success (Odeleye & Santiago, 2019).

Theoretical Framework

This study will be analyzed using Intersectionality as the primary framework. Incepted by Crenshaw in 1989, intersectionality acknowledges the interdependent essence of a multitude of social identities (Brooms et al., 2019; Nguyen & Nguyen, 2018). At the start of their collegiate career, first-gen students feel “invalidated by their identities” (Green, 2023, p. 67). Using an intersectional lens, research suggests that advisors can be more cognizant of the needs of first-generation students and develop a more individualized support plan (Nguyen & Nguyen, 2018). Rooted in research, the benefits of an intersectional approach to advising include recognizing diverse backgrounds, addressing systemic barriers, and providing holistic support rather than just academics (Helget, 2022). Holistically supporting the student is the foundation of student advising (Ward et al., 2012).

Validation Theory is the second component within the framework. This theory emerged from examining the success of first-generation students to understand what sustained them through graduation (Kezar et al., 2022). Contriving validation theory in advising this population of students, institutions can create a nurturing line of support that fosters success and retention (Coronella, 2018). According to validation theory, students are more likely to engage academically when they are acknowledged and receive support related to their identity. Rendon says, “Within the framework of validation theory, students need to feel validated in their identity as college students to reach their academic potential” (Green, 2023, p. 78). Here, Rendon’s theory emphasizes the importance of

fostering a sense of validation in students to increase their academic success. Rendon's Validation Theory considers the idea that most college environments were not devised with the need for the success of first-generation students at the forefront (Green, 2023). Advisors are said to be key in accommodating the desire to be recognized and enhancing the student's sense of confidence to make up for the deficit of "not knowing," (Strayhorn, 2015). Tactics employed by advisors through the validation theory approach include initiating contact, remaining consistent, positive reinforcement, and providing resources to foster positive experiences both inside and outside of the classroom (Coronella, 2018; Goldman et al., 2022).

First-generation students often attribute their disadvantages to their lack of knowledge relative to the collegiate environment, academic requirements, and their motivations to succeed to their level of independence and sense of identity (Green, 2023). This is where intersectionality and validation bridge. Academic and social integration are equally important when evaluating the likelihood of a student matriculating from one academic year to the next (Nava, 2010). The ubiquitous indication from the literature is that first-generation college students face more challenges than continuing-generation constituents which can limit their persistence and success (Rehr et al., 2022).

First-Generation Student Challenges

During their collegiate career students become more independent, become exposed to diverse groups of people, emerge in new environments, and begin to navigate their way through the expectancies of society. For any student, the transition to college can be taxing (Swanbrow Becker et al., 2017). For first-generation college students, the stress level is intensified due to the lack of familial support and necessary tools to

successfully adapt to their new academic environment (Swanbrow Becker et al., 2017). Qualitative studies show that the stigma of being a first-generation student comes with the notion that they lack immediate access to the necessary resources. According to research, the lack of resources culminates in an experience of obstacles, which are categorized into themes such as academic, financial, social, and psychological (Swanbrow Becker et al., 2017).

Academic

First-generation students often lack knowledge about college applications and academic requirements as well as academic resources once admitted (Bell et al., 2018; Nava, 2010). This lack of information can hinder their ability to make informed decisions, navigate the college admissions process, or seek help when necessary to tackle challenging coursework. This leads to disparities in academic preparedness compared to their continuing generation peers who come from families with college-educated parents (Nava, 2010). This disparity can result in difficulties in adjusting to college-level coursework and may require additional support to bridge the academic gap.

Financial

A strong percentage of first-generation students come from low-income backgrounds (Rehr et al., 2022; Scanlon, 2020), making it challenging to afford tuition, textbooks, and other educational expenses. Financial burdens can prompt these students to work longer hours, limiting their time to focus on academics and be involved on campus (Rehr et al., 2022). A lack of familiarity with the financial aid process, including scholarships, grants, work-study, and loans often results in missed opportunities for assistance, heightening their financial burden (Rehr et al., 2022; Scanlon, 2020).

Social

As previously mentioned, first-generation students lack the exchange of knowledge with family members who have experienced college, particularly to obtain a four-year degree. According to Maher (2015), this leaves students with doubt, declining confidence, and weary of their likelihood to matriculate. Gaining a feeling of inclusiveness within the college collective seems almost impossible. Students from lower socioeconomic backgrounds struggle with this the most (Kezar et al., 2022). As a result, social integration suffers and dissatisfaction with their overall collegiate career grows.

Psychological

In the focus on increasing retention rates in first-generation college students, researchers often fail to address their psychological needs (Swanbrow Becker et al., 2017). These students often experience higher stress levels, lower satisfaction, and a greater feeling of inferiority than their continuing generation peers (Swanbrow Becker et al., 2017). Imposter syndrome is essentially self-doubt that creates a feeling in students that they do not belong or deserve to be in college (Bell et al., 2018). This self-doubt undermines their confidence, motivation, and academic performance. Increased stress, anxiety, and depression due to the strain of balancing academic responsibilities, financial burden, and social transition just further compounds these issues creating an overall poor collegiate experience (Bell et al., 2018; Swanbrow Becker et al., 2017). To aid in overcoming these challenges research suggests outreach and support programs, and intentional student advising.

Best Practices

Academic Advising

Advisors play a notable role in supporting first-generation students by providing guidance, resources, and mentorship throughout their collegiate experience. They are the few personnel who develop deep connections with students to aid in their matriculation through graduation (Swecker et al., 2013). Academic advisors know the student's degree plan requirements and help them navigate course selections (Aljohani et al., 2023). They provide guidance on course requirements, prerequisites, and degree planning to ensure students stay on track toward completion (Aljohani et al., 2023; Larson et al., 2018). Study skills and other academic resources such as time management may also be provided (Aljohani et al., 2023).

Research shows that the practice of academic advising positively influences retention in students (Swecker et al., 2013). Formerly known as intrusive advising, proactive advising is recommended to get ahead of potential barriers for at-risk students (Swecker et al., 2013). Proactive advising increases student satisfaction by making initial contact and establishing a relationship, which is the responsibility of the advisor and not the student (Swecker et al., 2013). The impact of advisors on first-generation college students is significant in promoting academic success, personal development, and retention rates (Aljohani et al., 2023; Larson et al., 2018). By addressing the challenges faced by first-generation students and providing population-specific support, advisor roles become instrumental in helping these students navigate the intricacies of higher education. Further research is needed to explore additional strategies and interventions

that can enhance the impact of advising, specifically, on first-generation college students' overall college experience.

Student Organizations

Student organizations targeting first-generation college students typically possess several key characteristics. They provide a sense of community and belonging, allowing students to connect with peers who share similar backgrounds and are facing similar obstacles (Vaughan et al., 2020). These organizations often offer mentorship programs, pairing first-generation students with upperclassmen who can provide guidance (College Raptor Staff, 2020). Additionally, these organizations frequently organize workshops, seminars, and information sessions to help students navigate the complexities of college life, including academic expectations, financial aid, and career planning (College Raptor Staff, 2020).

Participation in organizations tailored for first-generation college students can harvest substantial benefits. They encourage self-efficacy and aid in motivating and helping students build confidence in their abilities to succeed academically (Odeley & Santiago, 2019). The supportive network leads to an upward trend in retention rates among first-generation students, reducing feelings of isolation and boosting overall well-being. Research suggests that engagement in these organizations develops students' social and leadership skills, as they often have opportunities to organize events, participate in community service, and develop advocacy initiatives (Inkelas et al., 2007). Studies have also shown that involvement in the organizations is associated with higher grades, motivated matriculation toward graduation, and improved satisfaction throughout their collegiate experience (Inkelas et al., 2007; Wibrowski et al., 2017). Students who

participate in these tailored organizations often report feeling more connected to their institution, which can contribute to a greater sense of belonging and aid in developing identities (Green, 2023; Odeley & Santiago, 2019). This reduces the feeling of imposter syndrome.

While organizations for first-generation college students offer numerous benefits, they also face challenges. Limited resources, such as funding and access to qualified staff, can lower the effectiveness of student organizations. Additionally, reaching and engaging all first-generation students on campus can be challenging, as some students may not be aware of the existence or benefits of these first-generation tailored organizations (Vaughan et al., 2020). Empowerment for first-generation students to overcome challenges and thrive in their collegiate environment is employed by providing a sense of community, mentorship, and resources (College Raptor Staff, 2020). The benefit of participation extends beyond academic achievement, contributing to increased retention rates, improved satisfaction, and a sense of belonging (Green, 2023; Odeley & Santiago, 2019). While challenges exist, continued research and support for these organizations can ensure that first-generation college students receive the necessary support to excel in their educational pursuits.

Summary

First-generation students face additional challenges throughout their collegiate journey compared to their continuing-generation counterparts. The challenges can be academic, social, financial, or psychological. This population of students notes that their disadvantages stem from the lack of resources and tools provided to them by their families. To overcome these obstacles and help these students successfully matriculate

through college, institutions employ proactive academic advising tactics and provide support through organizations tailored to first-generation college students. Proactive advising aims to get ahead of the needs of these students and provide them with the knowledge of potential resources upfront. Tailored student organizations work to provide a welcoming space for these students, giving them a sense of community while making connections with peers from similar backgrounds. Both first-generation advising, and student groups geared towards them foster student satisfaction, increase academic performance, teach soft skills such as time management, and effective studying, and promote personal development. All of which are encompassing the factors that are important to retaining first-generation college students. Further research on the retention of first-generation college students and the relationship with academic advising will help to gain a deeper understanding of how to better support this student population. By identifying the specific challenges and addressing them correctly within the context of academic advising, institutions of higher education can work towards creating a system for academic advising that fosters the success of these students.

CHAPTER III — METHODOLOGY

The purpose of this qualitative study was to better understand the magnitude of the advising relationship between academic advisors and first-generation college students. The study also investigated the challenges faced by this population and the approaches taken by advisors to provide the necessary support to these students.

1. What challenges do first-generation college students face in their collegiate experience?
2. What is the relationship between retention and advising interventions for first-generation college student populations?
3. Are first-generation student groups effective in supporting the student?

Research Design

Driven by Validation Theory and Intersectionality, this qualitative study sought to examine the advisor's perspective on their relationship with the retention of first-generation college students and how they help combat the challenges faced by students. Qualitative research allows one to measure data and ask questions that would increase the level of complexity when put into numbers (Denny & Weckesser, 2002). Additionally, as this study aimed to understand the advisor's approach to the challenges of first-generation students, qualitative research helps better understand how participants confront an obstacle given specific circumstances (Tenny et al., 2022). According to Denny & Weckesser (2002), the data in qualitative research is not fixed but continues until common themes in experiences and perceptions emerge. Using semi-structured interviews with pre-determined questions allowed for further discussion of the perspectives and experiences of the advisors. Qualitative research is suitable for smaller

sample sizes (Denny & Weckesser, 2002) and the population for this sample was relatively small.

Research Setting

Data for this study was collected at Abilene Christian University (ACU), a large, private, four-year, Christian institution that serves the southwest area. It is located in Abilene, Texas with a remote campus in Dallas, Texas. Texas ranks fifth in the nation of states with the highest number of first-generation college students (Hamilton, 2023). ACU was selected because, according to a U.S. News and World Report, it ranked highest for four years in a row in institutions focused on student success (Kilmer, 2022). In the Spring of 2020, *IGEN*, a student success program that notes the challenge in retention of this population of students and aims to provide resources to students during their collegiate experience, was launched.

Population and Participants

The population for this study included current undergraduate academic advisors who served first-generation college students in their caseload. No other criterion was selected to ensure diverse perspectives from advisors of all demographics. To mitigate unintended influence and coercion, IRB approval was obtained and an invitation to participate in an interview was sent to all 13 academic advisors. Participation was voluntary. The study yielded a 46.1% response rate with six participants accepting the invitation to participate.

Instrument

For this study, the instrument used consisted of a nine-question interview protocol. An interview guide was developed to target each research question. The first subset of questions focused on building rapport and how advisors established trust in their relationships with the students, while the second set addressed the challenges faced by first-generation students from the advisor's perspective. The final section asked about the benefits of student groups that target this population of students. The interview ended by allowing the participants to share any additional information that they felt was necessary.

Data Collection

All 13 academic advisors at ACU were sent an invitation, by email, to participate in an audio-recorded interview for this study. Reminders were sent once a week, for three weeks, resulting in two additional emails after the initial invitation. In the email, advisors were provided an information letter outlining the details of the study. Advisors who were interested in participating were instructed to utilize the calendar link in the invitation to schedule their interview with the researcher. Once participants were scheduled, they were then sent a letter of consent to sign via email prior to their interview. The interviews were conducted over a period of four weeks. The interviews took place virtually on a video calling platform and with consent were audio-recorded. Audio recordings from the interviews were transcribed by the researcher.

Data Analysis

According to Braun & Clarke (2021), using a coding reliability thematic approach consists of early-on theme development by identifying those themes through coding and categorizing the most frequent concepts the participants spoke to concerning

the topic of study. This type of approach is commonly used to capture the perspectives of the participants and to emphasize experiential research (Braun & Clarke, 2021). In this study, the researcher sought to make connections and identify themes and patterns from the collected data. This helped gain insight into the participant's experiences advising first-generation college students and their perspectives on the needs of this population. This strengthens the validity and allows for comparison across studies. The study gathered qualitative data through interviews. Before beginning the analysis, all audio recordings of the interviews were carefully converted into written transcripts and coded for analysis.

Through continuous comparison, the researcher categorized the recurring ideas of the participants into three common themes: Identity, Sense of Belonging, and Support. The themes were then broken down into sub-themes, or categories, as the researcher continued to analyze the data. The subcategories under the identity theme were values and status. Social groups fell under a sense of belonging while support was broken down into subthemes of preparedness and mentorship. Preparedness was further divided into two specific aspects such as finances and academics.

Each theme is supported by direct quotes and examples from the data to illuminate their significance and aid in understanding interpretation. Further steps in the analysis included critically assessing the identified themes to determine their relation to the existing literature and relevance to the research questions and objectives. Once this was complete, the results were extracted from the findings and further compared.

CHAPTER IV — RESULTS

This research sought to gain a deeper understanding of the barriers first-generation college students encounter while exploring the impact of academic advising on their retention. This study specifically aims to analyze the relationship between the advisor and the first-generation student. The data provides a look into the strategies used to support this population of students as they matriculate through their collegiate experience.

Participants

This chapter presents findings from the interviews with six academic advisors who advise students who identify as first-generation in their caseload. The participants are all from Abilene Christian University in Abilene, Texas. Each academic advisor worked with the first-generation student population. No other demographic or identifying characteristics were obtained in the participant profiles. The advisors first learned of their student's first-generation status at student orientation through the completion of a questionnaire that was made available to the advisors. First contact between the student and advisor takes place during their SOAR (Student Orientation, Advising, and Registration) session. Initial contact is brief as there is a large population that the advisors need to get through in a short amount of time.

Results

The findings illuminate three common themes relative to the retention of first-generation college students: (1) Sense of Belonging, (2) Trust, and (3) Support. Each theme can then be further divided into subcategories. Although the retention of this

population is complex and impacted by several factors, these were most prevalent among this group of participants. The findings will be organized by research questions.

Q1: What challenges do first-generation college students face in their collegiate experience?

Participants believe that this population struggles with navigating the demands of their collegiate education. The lack of familial guidance was said to be prevalent in these students leaving them unsure of what to expect. This uncertainty results in feeling isolated and confused and in return makes it difficult for these students to advocate for themselves or ask for help. Participant 2 provided an example of when they felt a student found self-advocacy challenging.

Sometimes it's just hey, here's how we need to navigate this, and you know, I, I meet with students quite often where they're like, I need I think I need to talk to my professor. I don't really know what to say I don't really and so you know, we have that conversation of hey, how about if you email them? And let's or email me first with what you think you should say and let me kind of help guide that because maybe the parents are involved. Maybe the kid doesn't want the parents involved. They don't want them to know their grades, not great or whatever. And so, I try to step in and in play a little bit of an advisor slash parent role.

Many first-generation students come from backgrounds where attending college is less common, leading to limited knowledge about college processes such as financial aid applications, course selection, and navigating campus resources. They are often not aware of what resources are available to them on campus. Participant 1 explained how lacking first-hand knowledge of the college experience from the parent poses a challenge.

Not having the knowledge that other students come in with whose parents possibly attended. Just not knowing what questions to ask. That's what I see. It seems like the ones who are not first generation have a little bit of a better handle on the whole experience as a whole as far as application scholarships, testing all of those things. The first-generation students just lacked some of the guidance just because their parents don't know how to guide them.

As did they all, participant 3 outlined that first-generation students have trouble not only learning of the resources available to them on campus but also how to take advantage and use them to their benefit.

I think, the hardest part for First Gen. That I've noticed outside of just, you know, understanding and recognizing what resources are on campus? And how to utilize those and how, like, I mean, even just signing up for tutoring, it's like, well, how do I go about that? And what is that? And what does that look like? Just understanding those college resources is a little bit different here than being in high school.

Another significant challenge faced by first-generation students is balancing academic responsibilities with other obligations on their own. Students are new to having the freedom and responsibility of following schedules at their leisure without the assistance of a bell. Early morning courses can be tough and finding the balance to ensure success is important. Participant 6 expresses this challenge.

A lot of times it's an eight o'clock class and they're like, I just don't I just don't like eight o'clock. Well, I understand I don't like eight o'clock either. I don't love

coming to work at eight o'clock. But I don't have an option. And so that's something that you're going to need to overcome pretty quickly.

Q2: What is the relationship between retention and advising interventions for first-generation college student populations?

Before describing the strategies they employed to retain first-generation students specifically, each participant had the opportunity to define success and how they measure it within their students.

Participant 1: It has a lot to do with their self-esteem, their self-worth, if they are doing what they love, or at least what they're interested in. They're enjoying it. They're getting up in the morning. they're completing assignments, they're meeting people, they're involved with other people. Those are the signs to me of success. This is working we're getting through this process successfully. Grades may or may not be A's and B's. But if we're passing and works getting work done, we're showing up, then I feel there's a measure of success there.

Success is equated to self-esteem and the effort the student puts in to work toward graduation. Participant 1 feels that making an effort is a sign of success. They believe that recognizing personal achievements, even if small, is a measure of success.

Participant 2: My definition of success just overall, is just more theoretical than anything else. It's like, what are you trying to achieve? And did you actually achieve that? I would put simply say achieving your goals even if you have to overcome adversity to do it, is success. As far as measurement, we use several metrics. We talked about first year retention rates, that's a measurement of overall cohort success. But overall, it's are you making the grades that you need to stay in

your intended major? Are you progressing through that major in a timely way? And are you retaining and succeeding academically with those metrics? Are you sleeping? Are you eating? Are you okay spiritually? Generally, academics take a backseat if those things aren't being paid attention to also.

For many of the participants, success was measured by more than academics. Success is situational and tailored to the student and their current needs and situation. Each student is aiming to achieve something different. For some, it is higher grades. For others, it is maximizing the amount of effort they put forth.

Participant 3: One of the ways I define success for them is keeping their appointments. You know, we go, we have campaigns that we send to our students to encourage them to meet with us, but obviously I can't make students come in and meet with me for advising. I think when they keep their appointments and when they make the appointments that shows success. So, I guess measuring it is just, you know, looking at their success in the classroom, obviously, if they're keeping up with their homework and attendance, you know, their grades are going to show it.

Additionally, reliability, commitment, and consistency are characteristics used to gauge success in first-generation students. Keeping their appointments, meeting deadlines, and maintaining attendance are seen in a positive light to the advisors.

Participant 4: The definition varies per student just based on academic ability and academic strength. That is why they're here. I also look at are they plugging in are they getting involved? It's so beneficial for them to not just plug in in class or go to class and go through the motions but to find a friend group, find a social club,

whether it's a fraternity and sorority, that doesn't matter, but there's so many other social clubs here at ACU that they can be involved in. It isn't even a fraternity or sorority and just getting involved within their department within the student life aspect. My expectations look different for different students.

Some of the advisors measured success by the student's belief or ability to meet their goals or level of engagement. If the students were staying on top of their responsibilities and connecting socially with their peers, they were lower on the advisors' radar for at-risk students.

Participant 5: How students find success in general can be tricky territory because sometimes they are approaching their college experience even down to an individual course with a version of success that has been given to them by parents. Given the particulars of their situation at this point in time, the definition of success really changes depending on the student and I think that that's necessary. Even for some first-gen students who are high achievers, they can go through, and they can make A's and B's and they can say I want to achieve a 3.5 and get into a good graduate program and they can meet that criteria. That's great and I want to support them in meeting their definition of success.

Other advisors believe that measuring success is complicated. The definition is unique to the student and is measured accordingly among the advisors at ACU.

Participant 6: I mean, success is a lot of competence. It's feeling competent in the path that they're on. Success to me is competence. It's not really about the grades, but it's just that they feel really good about the choices they've made. With competence they will continue to excel even if they change their program 10

times in the next four years. As long as they're confident then they will ask the questions they need to ask to put themselves in a great situation. So, I guess competence would be the one-word definition for me.

Success means something different for each student. Whether based on competence, grade point average, or consistency each advisor is mindful of the approach they take with their students.

Sense of Belonging

The sense of belonging in first-generation students is often fashioned by their past experiences and current challenges. Academic Advisors believe that they play an important role in the personal development of this population.

Participant 1: My biggest focus at the start is making them feel welcome and comfortable letting them know that I'm on their team, and I'm here to advocate for them.

By setting attainable goals and providing tailored support, advisors believe they empower first-generation students to overcome obstacles that may cause delays in their matriculation. Academic Advisors are intentional in ensuring that students don't feel at a disadvantage as they matriculate, but instead feel accomplished.

Participant 4: There's a whole lot that we're all learning. I'm very transparent about that because I don't want a student or a parent to sit in my office or entrust me with their child and their kid's education and think that they are beneath or below because they don't understand. I want them to know and ask all the questions.

Academic Advisors understand the social needs necessary for success during their student's collegiate experience.

Participant 1: If they have connections with good healthy friendships, if they're connecting with their professors, if they feel like they're being heard and they're being seen without those groups [tailored student groups] then I don't insist that they become you know, become a part of them. But if they seem to be you know, kind of not connected anywhere not finding people that are their people then I do direct them that way.

When students engage and are connected with other individuals, they feel a greater sense of belonging. Advisors believe they can foster a sense of belonging by encouraging engagement in campus activities and connecting students with peer groups.

Trust

The participants agree that by establishing rapport, they create safe spaces and open environments where students can come to express their concerns and ask for support.

Participant 6: Starting with those personal questions is a big piece of it because usually they're just going to naturally just relax when they start talking about personal stuff. A lot of times they're really like their stress levels high when they're first starting out. Things are uncertain. Once I get to know the students better and they feel more comfortable. I think part of maintaining that level of trust is asking them things.

This trust is built through intentional communication to establish a personalized connection. This level of connection leaves advisors under the impression that

uncertainty in this population of students can be eliminated and that reducing uncertainty increases retention.

Participant 5: I apply many of those same principles of joining empathetic listening, validation, sharing of common experience asking probing questions and so even down to the specific questions that I asked from students, they tend to be very open-ended, they tend to be very inviting. I can't say I do this perfectly every day, but I do my best to create a very warm and inviting environment for those students so that even when they step into my office before any words are spoken, they can feel like they can let down their defenses and truly just engage openly in conversation.

Support

All advisors believed that the resources recommended to students varied. Although this population is all considered first-generation, each student comes into college with a different background, and they are not always aware of the resources available to them.

Participant 2: I think the hardest part for First Gen that I've noticed outside of just, you know, understanding and recognizing what resources are on campus and how to utilize those and how, like, I mean, even just signing up for tutoring, it's like, well, how do I go about that? And what is that? And what does that look like? Just understanding those college resources, is a little bit different here than in high school.

Depending on what the student needs, support, resources, or other information is provided by the advisor.

Participant 1: Depending on what's needed, there's academic support through tutoring. We have a career development center. And resources for financial aid, medical care, counseling, all the different resources that are offered to all of our students.

Recommended resources or referrals include tutoring services, Grammarly, the library, the writing and speaking center, financial aid, LinkedIn Learning, or specific social groups.

Q3: Are first-generation student groups effective in supporting students?

Advisors do not feel that student groups are one size fits all. No participant was familiar with the on-campus student group, *IGEN*. They were familiar with other groups such as TRIO-SSS.

Participant 1: I think it's a good resource for them if they as I said, if they don't have another group that they're a part of and engaged with. It's not for — I don't think it's for everyone. I don't think everyone needs it. If they have connections with good healthy friendships, if they're connecting with their professors, if they feel like they're being heard and they're being seen without those groups then I don't, I don't insist that they become you know, become a part of them.

The participant felt that student groups geared towards first-generation students had the potential to be beneficial, but they were not a necessity for the student to be successful.

Participant 4: I want students to know that if it helps being involved in student organizations where they are amongst other students and maybe not afraid to ask questions - just to be in a group with other students who are kind of navigating the

same waters, unknown waters, is beneficial because it just helps you see that you're not the only one. You're not on an island by yourself.

The participants placed emphasis on the importance of tailored support and resources to help first-generation students navigate challenges effectively, ensuring they have access to both academic and social groups that are unique to their needs but only if they do not feel supported or connected to any other group or individual.

Discussion

The relationship between the retention of first-generation college students and academic advising is a critical area of research to explore, particularly as higher education institutions strive to improve outcomes for this population. Essentially, this study supports the idea that students whose parents lack collegiate experience face amplified challenges during their matriculation (McCulloh, 2022; Palbusa & Gauvain, 2017; Peralta & Klonowski, 2017; Ward et al., 2012). This aligns with the perspectives shared by academic advisors who recognize the barriers faced by first-generation students.

First-generation students face substantial challenges that alter their college experience relative to the social (Maher, 2015), financial (Rehr et al., 2022), academic (Bell et al., 2018; Nava, 2010), and psychological (Swanbrow Becker et al., 2017) factors in their lives. The findings show that academic advisors agree that having a sense of uncertainty or lack of self-efficacy undermines their confidence in navigating collegiate life. Low social integration leads to self-doubt and as a domino effect, other areas of the student's collegiate experience suffer (Maher, 2015). The participants highlight the idea that if the nonacademic factors are not being taken care of, other areas in their experience

also show a decline, even if slight. The participants did not highlight any aspect of financial strain that this population of students faced or how to combat it.

Academically, research shows that this population of students begins college feeling less prepared than continuing-generation college students (Bell et al., 2018; Nava, 2010). The participants in this study did not agree or disagree with the research. It was emphasized that although there are common barriers among first-generation students there are still some needs that are unique to the student. As a result, resources are provided as the need arises. The most common observation was that these students were less inclined to know where to find academic assistance or ask for help when it was needed. Swanbrow Becker et al. (2017) note that they often see higher levels of stress in these students when trying to balance responsibilities. Participant beliefs did, however, explicitly align with this statement. Good standing in academics was viewed as a common measurement of success in this population but not the only measurement.

Additionally, the advisors' insights into the relationship with first-generation students hold true to Rendon's Validation Theory. Supporting students through positive affirmation and fostering a sense of belonging is a common approach. The psychological aspect of self-efficacy plays a critical role in their retention and matriculation. Many first-generation students doubt their capabilities due to a lack of familial support from not having a parent who has gone through what they are experiencing (Arch & Gilman, 2019). The findings indicate that these challenges are not surface level. Each advisor intentionally seeks to develop relationships with their first-generation students to enact strategies such as acknowledging strengths, encouraging persistence, reassuring belonging, and encouraging engagement. These actions align with Rendon's theory and

the idea that validation and support impact academic success and personal development and in return foster success among this population.

The perspectives of the participants in this study align with research that indicates that effective advising provides first-generation students with the required social, academic, and psychological support needed to matriculate successfully (Swanbrow Becker et al., 2017). The perspectives show that support is given through consistent interaction, reducing feelings of isolation, and redirection to specialized resources. Participant beliefs align with the research in the instance that student groups directed towards first-generation students can cater to the needs of the student in very similar ways as advising (Inkelas et al., 2007). They believe student groups can help provide a sense of belonging and community and combat self-doubt. This continues to support Rendon's Theory of Validation and how it impacts first-generation students.

Implications

As a result of this study, the researcher found that many of the perspectives of the academic advisors at ACU align with the literature about the relationship between academic advisors and the retention of first-generation college students. Insight is provided into how the practice of academic advising can continue to improve to the benefit of this population of students through more personable approaches. From the interviews, much of the literature was reiterated. One can see that prior research done on the relationship between these two populations is accurate.

Best practices include proactive advising or making the initial contact and building a relationship. Implications on the practice of academic advising made clear from this study include continuing to address the social, academic, and psychological

barriers upfront with the student before they cause more severe issues during their matriculation. Ultimately, continuing to explore this topic will create a well-rounded practice that captures a holistic view of the student. In return, this will help to improve the retention rates of this student population.

The significance of this study was to understand the relationship between the retention of first-generation students and academic advising. Understanding how academic advisors can support this population of students allows institutions the opportunity to develop targeted interventions that improve retention. Such interventions could include tailored training programs for the advisors that equip them with the skills and ability to address the needs of first-generation students. The findings can also be used to review or improve academic policies surrounding this practice and the reporting of this population. Not only can this research help inform policy decisions at the institutional level but at the systemic level as well. With a robust connection between effective advising practices and increased retention rates among first-generation students, institutions may advocate for or allocate more resources towards enhancing advising services or intentionally pairing these students with experienced advisors. Additionally, findings from this study could influence funding opportunities aimed at at-risk populations in higher education. Understanding this relationship not only benefits first-generation college students but also promotes equity and diversity. As universities strive to create equitable educational experiences, understanding how academic advising influences retention will be crucial in shaping policies that indirectly promote inclusivity across diverse populations. It can contribute to a broader DEI framework by ensuring that

all students receive equitable support tailored to their unique circumstances, allowing them to be retained.

Limitations

Limitations are elements in a research design that the researcher is unable to control. For this study, one limitation was subjectiveness. The researcher was left to interpret the data from the interviews. The intended perspective of the participant could differ from what the researcher interpreted, skewing the results. Another limitation is that the data was collected from a small, very specific sample. This makes the data hard to generalize to other populations.

Recommendations

The goal of this study was to explore the relationship between the retention of first-generation college students and their academic advisors. The results show that academic advising is critical to the success of this student population at the expense of their social, academic, psychological, and financial well-being. Recommendations to maximize findings include expanding the pool of participants across institutions. This will add variety to not only the institution type but also the pool of first-generation students being referenced. Future researchers could also find benefit from including the perspectives of the first-generation students themselves. This could help to enhance the validity, making the results more generalizable. Other recommendations include finding creative yet direct ways to incorporate the financial strain and barriers of these students into the conversation. If the advisor is initiating contact and conversation in the other three categories of types of challenges these students face then finances should be of importance, as well. Last, the researcher may find benefit in a longitudinal study or

following how advising approaches impact the student's retention across semesters. This will help gain insight into the trends of both short and long-term effects.

Conclusion

This qualitative study highlighted the relationship between academic advising and first-generation college students. The results suggest effective advising supports the student by addressing their needs on an academic, psychological, social, and financial level. Through in-depth interviews, participants gave perspective into how personalized guidance encourages academic performance by strengthening validation and a sense of belonging. This study emphasized the importance of proactive advising strategies such as tailored resources and initiating contact. As institutions aim to improve the retention of first-generation college students it is important to prioritize academic advising. This research provided insight into the approaches academic advisors take to support their first-generation students throughout their academic journeys.

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APPENDIX A — IRB Approval Letter

Office of Research Integrity

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NOTICE OF INSTITUTIONAL REVIEW BOARD ACTION

The project below has been reviewed by The University of Southern Mississippi Institutional Review Board in accordance with Federal Drug Administration regulations (21 CFR 26, 111), Department of Health and Human Services regulations (45 CFR Part 46), and University Policy to ensure:

- The risks to subjects are minimized and reasonable in relation to the anticipated benefits.
- The selection of subjects is equitable.
- Informed consent is adequate and appropriately documented.
- Where appropriate, the research plan makes adequate provisions for monitoring the data collected to ensure the safety of the subjects.
- Where appropriate, there are adequate provisions to protect the privacy of subjects and to maintain the confidentiality of all data.
- Appropriate additional safeguards have been included to protect vulnerable subjects.
- Any unanticipated, serious, or continuing problems encountered involving risks to subjects must be reported immediately. Problems should be reported to ORI using the Incident form available in InfoEd.
- The period of approval is twelve months. If a project will exceed twelve months, a request should be submitted to ORI using the Renewal form available in InfoEd prior to the expiration date.

PROTOCOL NUMBER: 23-0924
PROJECT TITLE: EXPLORING THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN FIRST-GENERATION COLLEGE STUDENT RETENTION AND ADVISING: THE ADVISORS PERSPECTIVE
SCHOOL/PROGRAM Educational Research & Administration
RESEARCHERS: PI: Mariana McKoy
Investigators: McKoy, Mariana~Tontz, Paul Andrew~
IRB COMMITTEE ACTION: Approved
CATEGORY: Expedited Category
PERIOD OF APPROVAL: 26-Feb-2024 to 25-Feb-2025

Donald Sacco

Donald Sacco, Ph.D.
Institutional Review Board Chairperson